

FOSSR

FOSTERING OPEN SCIENCE IN SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH

DELIVERABLE 8.3

FIRST REPORT ON INITIATIVES RELATED TO CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRAINING (ONLINE COURSES, LEARNING SESSION AND ACTION RESEARCH SESSION, HIGHER EDUCATION COURSES)

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<i>Abstract</i>	This deliverable details the progress and outcomes of activities undertaken in tasks 8.1, 8.2, and 8.3 of Work Package 8 (WP8) "Capacity Building and Training" of the FOSSR project during the first 18 months. It demonstrates the achievement of the milestones 8 and 10 linked to the Work Package.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The background mission of the FOSSR project relies on creating and strengthening awareness and knowledge of data and methodologies used in empirical social sciences among a wide audience, through maintaining and reinforcing relevant Research Infrastructures (RI), while fostering the development of a research and social environment conducive to an open, shared and simplified data access via innovative interfaces. The project will concretely contribute to the effective implementation of the ‘open science’ for social science researchers by providing innovative tools and services for research, shared virtual environment for data access and a wide and varied package of training courses, sessions and programmes (FOSSR DoW, 2022).

FOSSR adopts the common theme of the development of Open Science in the Italian context with the goal of creating a framework of tools and services for the social science scholar community involving the RIs in social sciences coordinated by CNR, namely CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS. The framework should take the form of an integrated knowledge sharing platform, a single point of access to all the tools and services made available by the Italian nodes of social science infrastructures.

FOSSR fosters the building of an Italian Open Science Cloud, along the lines of the European Open Science Cloud project, in which to integrate innovative services developed by the project for data collection, data curation and fairness and data analysis on economic and societal change.

FOSSR wants to promote toward multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces.

1.1 FOSSR objectives and ambition

FOSSR has the general aim of promoting, towards multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, by providing (i) systematic and organized knowledge (also through summary harmonized data) about available social science data resources in Italian data archives, especially the CESSDA Archive, already object of the grand infrastructural proposal; (ii) resources supporting methodological advancement as to data collection and data analysis, especially important for RISIS to understand the design, the implementation, and the outcome of research and innovation policies, which can improve the robustness of empirical evidence produced for policy makers and to deal with new research questions, and (iii) tools and services to make publicly available advanced probability panels for longitudinal analyses to support important survey such as SHARE, complementing them with a network of online laboratories. The integration of this pool of resources shall concretely contribute to the realization of open science for scholars in social sciences, together with an important program of scientific training for the production and analysis in the field of social sciences based on FAIR empirical data.

One further key objective is setting a new generation of young researchers in social sciences, by hiring several researchers and technologists with fixed time contracts, which will become highly skilled human resources in data science and data management in social science research, and by funding PhD positions to train early career researchers in the field.

FOSSR is also aimed at fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces (data exploration portals, time series, interactive visualizations), and through online data analysis software aimed at students, along with divulgation of resources about social science methodology. These aspects are particularly aimed at civil society organizations (NGOs, etc.), students, citizens, to foster a widespread societal awareness of social science data, results, methods, to promote an easier and more user-friendly dissemination.

The main investment shall be on the creation of a suitable IT infrastructure and a network of data center to provide researchers access online and onsite, and to support the workflow of the proposed collaborative projects. One of the subsequent goals of FOSSR will be to develop innovative tools and services for data collection and data analyses, and to support participating users in the acquisition and use of advanced equipment and software for social science research needed for collaborative studies and projects. The achievement of the above-mentioned goals can be reached by means of an online platform – the Open Cloud, acting also as a dissemination layer, intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring intermediation between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access also to multiple software interfaces, geared at different audiences, methodological content, and training materials.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

This deliverable details the progress and outcomes of the activities undertaken in tasks 8.1, 8.2, and 8.3 of Work Package 8 (WP8) "Capacity Building and Training" of the FOSSR project during the first 18 months. It also demonstrates the achievement of the milestones 8 and 10 linked to this work package.

The FOSSR WP8 aims to provide a **comprehensive range of training initiatives** designed to enhance individual skills in leveraging the full potential of the network of infrastructures and new services and tools involved in FOSSR. These initiatives will focus on advanced methods and techniques for data collection, management and analysis, as well as strategies for addressing new research questions for meeting societal needs.

The training courses and programmes target a diverse audience associated with research infrastructures, including scholars, early-career researchers, students, practitioners, policymakers, officers, and government officers.

As outlined in the Project's Description of Work (DoW), the initiatives are divided into three main categories:

1. **Online Training Courses** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 1**). These courses focus on specific topics related to data collection, management and processing, aiming to encourage researchers and interested individuals to access and utilize infrastructure data.
2. **Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 2**). Participatory sessions aimed at learning how the efforts of researchers can meet the needs of societal actors and how infrastructure data can create social impacts.
3. **Course at Master level and positions at PhD level** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 3**). This includes Higher Education Programmes: a Master's course in applied data science and the creation of PhD positions at various Italian universities.

Section 2 of this document outlines the diversified range of training opportunities envisioned by WP8 Tasks 1-2-3. Section 3 reports on the activities developed within the Online Training Courses, as anticipated by WP Task 8.1. In Section 4, the activities carried out within the Participatory Sessions (Learning Session and Action Research Session) as planned by WP Task 8.2 are presented. Sections 5 and 6 delve into the progress of activities developed within Task 8.3 concerning the establishment of a Course at Master Level and the creation of PhD positions. Section 7 highlights the connection between WP8 activities and those developed by WP9. Section 8 provides a summary of the Milestones and Key Performance Indicators achieved by Task 8.1, Task 8.2, and Task 8.3 at Month 18 of the FOSSR project. Finally, Section 9 presents the document conclusions, while Section 10 specifies the acronyms used throughout the text.

2. BUILDING CAPACITIES FOR SOCIAL SCIENCE OPEN SCIENCE: THE VARIETY OF TRAINING INITIATIVES IN THE FOSSR PROJECT

The WP8 of FOSSR project is dedicated to enhancing the skills the capabilities of current and next generation of researchers, data scientists and relevant stakeholders in accessing, managing and analyzing social science data. It also fosters reflective learning and productive interactions between the research community and societal actors within the framework of Open Science.

Ensuring a **diversified range of training activities** is essential for advancing and promoting the content and services of infrastructural projects such as FOSSR, thereby building capacities to effectively utilize and benefit from available resources. Research infrastructures should enhance research by improving researchers' capabilities to conduct high-quality studies, meeting the needs of social and political stakeholders, and ultimately benefiting society as a whole. Thus, prioritizing the training of scientists and professionals is crucial, as it provides them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to effectively use and benefit from scientific data.

The innovative data collection and analysis methods and services developed in the FOSSR project's Work Packages 3, 4, and 5, along with the new data access and service utilization strategies proposed in WP6, aim to have a significant impact on the social science community. This impact could be amplified through initiatives broadening the range of researchers and stakeholders who can acquire and apply this knowledge, leading to new applications for these advanced resources.

WP8, coordinated by CNR-IRCrES, is offering a variety of training opportunities throughout the project duration. The portfolio includes:

- **Online Training Courses (OTC)**

Promoted within WP8 Task 8.1, and managed by CNR-IRPPS (UO4)

OTCs are short, intensive, two-day courses which aim to develop knowledge in advanced data analysis methods and techniques, as well as improve research data management skills in accordance with FAIR principles. The courses, operated remotely, target scholars, young researchers, students, and stakeholders from civil society, encouraging the use of quantitative approaches and access to FOSSR infrastructure data. **Methodological Courses** focus on solutions for socio-economic data collection and analysis developed by the Project, covering tools for developing surveys and innovative methods for knowledge representation. **Data Management Courses** aim to equip participants with the skills to manage the data lifecycle and effectively share data in an Open Science context. They promote the management of big data sets according to FAIR principles, GDPR regulations, and ethical considerations. The courses combine theoretical knowledge with interactive, hands-on work sessions.

- **Participatory sessions (PS, Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions)**

Promoted within WP8 Task 8.2, and managed by CNR-IRCrES (UO2)

These sessions, conducted in a hybrid format and lasting two days, facilitate the sharing of perspectives between researchers and social actors on utilizing FOSSR resources and services. The sessions aim to stimulate pathways for change in research and reflect on the social impact of data-generated knowledge. **Learning Sessions** promote active learning with expert guidance on leveraging FOSSR resources and services to address socially relevant issues. The goal is to identify training needs related to data exploitation, stimulate the shared development of solutions, and foster discussions and hands-on activities. **Action Research Sessions** guide participants in exploring concrete problems encountered in their research or research-related work to co-generate pathways for change. Moderated by an expert, they aim to stimulate transformative actions that address participants' "development questions". The participatory sessions are characterized by high levels of participant interaction. The target audience includes researchers, scholars in social research, and non-academic stakeholders.

- **Higher Education Programmes (Course at Master Level and PhD Positions)**

Coordinated within WP8 Task 8.3, jointly managed by CNR-ISMED and CNR-IRCrES (UO14 and UO2)

A key goal of FOSSR is to train a new generation of young researchers in the social sciences who can take advantage of opportunities related to Open Science. To this end, the Project signed a series of agreements with a number of prestigious Italian universities for creating Higher Education Programmes. A Second-level **Master Programme in Social Data Science**, lasting two years, has been activated at the University of Milan-Bicocca, intended as a programme that promotes a widespread knowledge of methodologies used in the empirical social sciences and the training of a new generation of researchers with strong expertise in the application to social sciences of techniques of data collection, analysis, visualization, reporting in a variety of situation (see par. 5 of this report). **Positions in PhD courses** related to the field of social sciences, on topics related to the contents of the FOSSR Project, have been created at some Italian Universities. The positions have been assigned in response to research project proposals coherent to the themes of the FOSSR project, with the goal of developing advanced skills in the field of social sciences, fostering effective research methodologies, allowing advanced analysis of complex data sets, and preparing for a complex use of statistical software. The doctoral positions, initially planned to be 20, were first reduced to 11 in agreement with the Ministry of University and Research (MUR), with a funding for the first 2 years, and finally 10 positions have been successfully opened (see par. 6 of this report).

3. REPORT ON ONLINE TRAINING COURSES

3.1 Generalities of the Online Training Courses

As FOSSR is committed to supporting the education of the next generation of data scientists, Task 8.1 of WP8, coordinated by CNR-IRPPS, organized and started implementing the Online Training Courses (OTC), that include: - **Methodological Courses (MC)** aimed at improving knowledge related to the application of advanced statistical methods and techniques, - **Research Data Management Courses (RDMC)**, addressed to social science researchers who want to acquire skills to manage and share data in compliance with FAIR principles.

For the entire duration of the FOSSR project, a total of 6 online training courses (MC+RDMC) are planned with the participation of at least 150 attendees.

The 2 types of courses are designed focusing on different issues and topics:

- Methodological Courses provide basic and advanced knowledge about the content of the FOSSR infrastructure, data collection and processing.
- Research Data Management Courses provide advanced knowledge on data management and data lifecycle in the research-related processes.

OTCs, which are free of charge of the participants, have been organized and implemented addressing some of the major goals presented in the DoW of the FOSSR project, with reference to WP8, namely: (i) developing and strengthening individual skills in utilizing the potential of infrastructures, using advanced tools and techniques to address innovative research questions; (ii) providing expertise in managing the research data lifecycle.

Methodological Courses (MC) and Research Data Management Courses (RDMC) have been proposed and organized based on FOSSR research community. The CNR institutes involved in the FOSSR project have been activated in response to a permanent call for proposal. Moreover, FOSSR project partners were constantly invited to submit proposals, with reference to their specific competences, the role played in the FOSSR project and their main scientific collaborations.

In the third course organized –“*From open data to open knowledge graphs: the role of semantic technologies*” – a hybridization of the two types of courses was provided, depending on the specific subject matter, in order to enhance scholars and stakeholders in gathering both competences, methodological and data management, as well as fostering reflective learning and interactions between researchers and stakeholders.

3.2 Description of the three Online Training Courses realized

As expected in the project DoW, by 30 April 2024 (bimester 9) three Online Training Courses were realized, marking the achievement of FOSSR *Milestone 8*:

- 1 Methodological Course;
- 1 Research Data Management Course;
- 1 Hybrid (Methodological and Research Data Management) course

As indicated in Table 1, an audience of 169 participants was involved (exceeding the KPI of 75 participants expected by the project DoW).

Table 1 – KPIs associated with the Online Training Courses of the FOSSR project (MCs and RDMs) at bimester 9.

<i>State</i>	<i>Milestone 8</i>	<i>WP Task</i>	<i>KPI</i>	<i>Deadline</i>
expected	First 3 Online courses delivered (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	3 courses delivered 75 attendees involved	Bimester 9 April 2024
achieved	First 3 Online courses delivered (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	3 courses delivered 169 attendees involved	Bimester 8 February 2024

All the courses were conducted online using Zoom software.

In the following lines, a description of the 3 online courses is provided.

All materials, tools and ppt presentations used for the courses were made available for the participants and a wider audience in the FOSSR Zenodo space¹.

1ST ONLINE TRAINING COURSE DATA LIFECYCLE AND ARCHITECTURES IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES

Dates: October 4th 5th 2023

Type of course: Methodological courses (MC)

Teachers: Loredana Cerbara, Nicolò Marchesini – CNR IRPPS

Audience: 26 participants

Short description: The best way to understand the potential of the FOSSR infrastructure is to know the entire life cycle of data and the reasons that lead to choices in terms of the type of production, storage and treatment methods that affect the quality of final data. The course dealt with the methodological choices in creating databases to answer research questions or fill information gaps relevant to society and institutions. In addition, the course enhanced the original data production potential offered by the FOSSR infrastructure, which stands in an intermediate slice of the market between the official production - of high quality but not very flexible and which requires a long preparation and a complex organisation - and the private production of data - characterised by the high speed of realisation but at the expense of quality. The course was devoted to both: young researchers, even in training, who want to approach the production, archiving and management of data, and those who, coming from other disciplines, do not have the necessary training to understand its potential fully, despite needing to use high-quality data.

Structure and contents: the course was structured in four modules, each built on frontal lessons, participatory and offline training activities. Each module lasted 2 hours + minimum 1 hour of exercises in the form of a soft laboratory in online mode, for a total of 12 hours:

- **Module 1. Data life cycle, data curation and preservation:** The module addressed the main issues that can arise from design to production and storage and finally to access and analysis.
- **Module 2. Data curation and conservation:** The main methods and tools for privacy and compliance with the GDPR 2016 were illustrated through some case histories: CNR practices. This last aspect will be taken care of together with the forthcoming course lecturers on data management. Even some platforms already in place (such as DASSI - Social Sciences Data Archives Italy -, Italian node of CESSDA) were shown as examples of data production and processing and as a possibility of interoperability between platforms.

¹ First online training course materials: <https://zenodo.org/records/8414669> ; Second online training course materials: <https://zenodo.org/records/10136335> ; Third online training course materials: <https://zenodo.org/records/10793529>

- Module 3. Data typologies and architectures in the social sciences different ways and methods that are appropriate to the data measurement level were presented. Students had the opportunity to create sample databases designed to apply a reading of information with statistical methods
- Module 4. Statistics for the social sciences: a general overview of the approaches and families of statistic methods generally used for the social sciences (an overview of quantitative and qualitative analysis were presented as a guide for those approaching this topic).

A detailed report of the course, with more data on contents, participants and assessment results is provided in *Annex 1*.

2ND ONLINE TRAINING COURSE MANAGING DATA WITHIN THE SOCIAL SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURES: THE ROLE OF FOSSR

Dates: November 6th 7th 2023

Type of course: Research Data Management courses (RDMC)

Teachers: Fabrizio Pecoraro (CON IRPPS), Lottie Provost (CNR-ILC); Carlo Maria Pisano (Università di Milano – Bicocca); Domingo Scisci (Università di Milano – Bicocca); Loredana Cerbara and Nicolò Marchesini (CNR-IRPPS).

Audience: 27 participants.

Short description: Main aim of this course was providing an overview about data quality and data management and how to manage scientific data based on the FOSSR framework. In particular, the course focused on FAIR data management and stewardship within the social science disciplines, providing the skills, tools, and standards required to embed Open Science in the research workflow such as: Open Science in Horizon Europe, Open Access in publishing, Research Data Management, FAIR principles, Open Data, and Data Management Plan. Moreover, legal and ethical aspects related to the management of non-personal and personal data will be explored. Specific case studies, good and worst practices were also analysed to capture their issues, strengths, weaknesses and opportunities.

The course was devoted to both young researchers, even in training, who want to approach the production, archiving and management of data, and those who, coming from other disciplines, do not have the necessary training to fully understand its potential, despite needing to use high-quality data.

Structure and contents: The course was structured in four on-line training modules, each one built on frontal lessons and several interactions and offline training activities:

- Module 1. Open data/access/science/...: the module was focused on research data, open data (basic concepts), clarifying why open data are strategic, how to publish open data. Moreover, a landscape analysis of the repositories adopted in the social sciences was proposed.

- Module 2. Data management plan: a case study/good practice from social science: the module clarified what a Data Management Plan is and what is the role of a data steward, through a presentation of the main problems to be faced in drafting a DMP. Moreover, the different types of metadata and their role in data discovery and reuse were presented, with reference to CESSDA and Share infrastructures.
- Module 3. Research Data Management: FAIR principles, Interoperability/standards: The module introduced the topic of research data management, discussing the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. Finally, some legal aspects related to the management of research results, such as copyright and open licenses (Creative Commons) were discussed.
- Module 4. Privacy and security: Legal and ethical aspects related to the management of non-personal and personal data, with an in-depth analysis of the application of the GDPR legislation in the context of funded projects were presented in the module.

The course was awarded with a university educational credit by University of Rome Tor Vergata, Communication Sciences, Prof. Claudia Hassan.

A detailed report of the course, with more data on contents, participants and assessment results is provided in *Annex 1*.

3RD ONLINE TRAINING COURSE FROM OPEN DATA TO OPEN KNOWLEDGE GRAPHS: THE ROLE OF SEMANTIC TECHNOLOGIES

Dates: February 28th 29th 2024

Type of course: Hybrid (Methodological and Research Data Management course)

Teachers: Andrea Giovanni Nuzzolese, Miguel Ceriani, Giorgia Lodi, Alessandro Russo (CNR-ISTC).

Audience: 116 participants

Short description: Main aim of this course was to understand how semantic technologies enable the creation of more efficient, reusable, interoperable, and accessible open datasets enhancing them to knowledge graphs. This is utmost important in FOSSR, which has a whole work package (i.e. WP5) dedicated to innovation in data analysis based on knowledge extraction, integration, and enrichment. During the course the following topics were discussed:

- RDF to design linked open datasets;
- SPARQL to query the linked open data cloud;
- OWL, ontology design patterns, and Protégé to design ontologies;
- RML to extract knowledge from structured sources to knowledge graphs;
- some prompting engineering to ask large language models to perform knowledge graph construction from unstructured sources.

Structure and contents: The course was structured in four on-line training modules, each one built on frontal lessons and several interactions and offline training activities:

- Module 1. Linked Open Data: the RDF to design linked open dataset was presented;
- Module 2. Querying knowledge graph with SPARQL: SPARQL as a way to query the linked open data cloud;
- Module 3. Ontology design: two issues were presented: OWL, ontology design patterns, and Protégé to design ontologies;
- Module 4. Knowledge extraction: the module presented RML as a tool to extract knowledge from structured sources to knowledge graphs.

A detailed report of the course, with more data on contents, participants and assessment results is provided in *Annex 1*.

3.3 The work process: steps and procedures

Management activities related to OTCs are coordinated by CNR-IRPPS. In general, it is expected that all CNR partners involved in FOSSR can submit proposals for organizing OTCs, and that the proposals include contents or topics from WP3-WP4-WP5-WP6 and relate to the infrastructures involved in FOSSR. Partners involved in FOSSR can organize training in partnership mode; all partners can participate in specific lectures or modules within training.

A process for submission and assessment of the training proposals (Standard Operating Process) coming from the FOSSR partners has been implemented (Details in *Annex 2*). According to this process, call for proposals (*Annex 3*) is circulated between the FOSSR partners. Proposals are submitted using dedicated formats for MCs and RDMCs, including dates, details about the content of the training and infrastructure(s) involved, an articulated program, targeted audience (specific skills requested to the participants), facilities supplied to the participants (*Annex 4*).

Proposals and expressions of educational needs can be submitted anytime throughout the duration of the project to: training.fossr@ircres.cnr.it.

A Training Committee is in charge of the approval of the proposals for MCs and RDMCs, composed by:

- Dr. Andrea Orazio Spinello (WP8 Leader);
- Dr. Adriana Valente (WP 8.1 Leader until March 31, 2024);
- Dr. Emanuela Reale (former Scientific Coordinator of the FOSSR Project).

Proposals for OTCs are assessed on the basis of the following requirements:

- Background of the subject(s) in charge of the training activities;
- Clarity of the proposal, clear added value of the course and relevance for the FOSSR aims;
- Precise identification of the targeted audience, considering that in case of courses based on advanced statistics, the audience shall have enough competences in order to benefit from the course;

- Facilities provided to the participants;
- In accordance with the NRRP principles: gender balance strategy and strategies adopted to enhance the participation of students from southern regions;
- Accessibility strategy: the training must be accessible for a wide community (including users' community);
- Inclusion strategy: how the participation of potential participants with fewer opportunities is enhanced and promoted;
- Methodological approach: level of students' participation and interactivity of the training;
- The applicant should explain how to assess the final level of knowledge acquired by participants during the course. It is welcome to include in the course practical and interactive exercises that also have the aim of (formative) evaluation. Otherwise, the applicant must explain the tools for assessment chosen (e.g.: final tests or composition);
- Presence of updated documentation to be supplied to the students (the documentation for Applied Courses is supposed to be updated according to the changes of the datasets and platforms);
- Sustainability: how the course may be reused by the scientific, educational and civil communities?;
- Communication strategy: the applicant is in charge to promote his/her own course, synergies with WP9 can be activated.

The idea is not to have a traditional “selection process”, rather a constructive process involving the Committee in charge of training management and the proposers, so that their proposals fit better with the FOSSR approach.

The Standard Operating Procedure

A Standard Operating Procedure (SOP see *Annex 2*) has been designed by Task 8.1 researchers in order, for all concerned actors – Task 8.1 researchers, WP8 leader, FOSSR management, Task 8.1 Training Committee, FOSSR communication officers, the OTC main promoters (PRP) – to be aligned with the process of proposal, validation, development, communication and evaluation of each OTC, so that all actors involved could be aware of initiatives, requirements and feedbacks needed at all steps of an OTC creation and development and of the relationships among all activities.

This procedure was debated with the WP8 leader and researchers, and, after agreement on all related issues and commitments, has been implemented throughout the entire life cycle of the OTCs.

4. REPORT ON PARTICIPATORY SESSIONS (LEARNING SESSIONS AND ACTION RESEARCH SESSIONS)

4.1 Generalities of the Participatory Sessions

FOSSR's participatory sessions share a common goal of fostering active engagement and collaborative problem-solving among participants, drawing on the principles of constructivist learning and action research methodologies.

Learning Sessions (LS) and Action Research Sessions (ARS) share a commitment to active participation, collaborative learning, and practical application. They are designed to move beyond the passive reception of knowledge and encourage participants to critically and creatively engage with real-world problems. By fostering an environment where learning and action are intertwined, FOSSR aims to enhance the research potential of social science infrastructures and generate tangible social impact.

Both formats emphasize the importance of participant-driven content and solutions, critical reflection, and the co-generation of knowledge, ultimately aiming to empower researchers and stakeholders to effectively address societal challenges.

CNR-IRCrES (UO2) is in charge of managing the Participatory Sessions (PS). CNR-IRCrES staff leads these sessions, which address the educational needs identified by partners concerning FOSSR infrastructures, project services, and accomplishments. The sessions are free of charge for the participants.

In the first year of the project, an expression of interest (*Annex 5*) was circulated among the FOSSR partners with the aim of collecting training needs. Based on the responses, we selected the topics and instructors for the first two participatory sessions (one Learning Session and one Action Research Session). We then held 3 preparatory meetings with the chosen instructors to outline the structure, methods, and specific topics of the sessions.

In the two months leading up to the events, a launch and promotion plan was developed, including a special poster, save the date, and registration form.

As expected in the project DoW, by 30 April 2024 (bimester 9) two participatory sessions were realized by CNR-IRCrES, marking the achievement of FOSSR *Milestone 10*:

- 1 Learning Session on 6-7 December 2023;
- 1 Action Research Session on 13 and 20 March 2024.

As indicated in Table 2, an audience of 44 participants was involved in total (exceeding the KPI of 40 participants expected by the project DoW). The list and profile of participants of both Sessions are presented in the Reports in *Annex 6 and 7*.

Table 2 – KPIs associated with the Participatory Sessions of the FOSSR project (LS and ARS) at bimester 9.

State	Milestone 10	WP Task	KPI	Deadline
expected	First 2 Learning session/Action Research Sessions delivered	Task 8.2	2 Learning session/ Action Research Sessions delivered; 40 participants involved	Bimester 9 April 2024
achieved	First 2 Learning session/Action Research Sessions delivered	Task 8.2	2 Learning session/ Action Research Sessions delivered; 44 participants involved	Bimester 9 March 2024

Both the sessions have been conducted in hybrid format, in presence at CNR-IRCrES venue in Rome, and online using Zoom and Teams tools.

Materials, tools and ppt presentations used for the sessions are made available for the participants and a wider audience in the FOSSR Community repository on Zenodo².

In the following lines, a description of the 2 participatory sessions is provided.

4.2 Description of the first Learning Session

The Learning Session "*Designing Socio-Economic Policy Evaluation: learning through FOSSR*" was based on a two-day program scheduled for December 6-7, 2023.

Local scientific/organising committee: Giovanni Cerulli, Serena Fabrizio, Andrea Orazio Spinello, Alessandra Maria Stilo, Emanuela Reale.

Due to the course format, participation in the learning session was limited to a maximum of 25 attendees. Participants were selected based on the relevance of their educational or professional background to the course topics, as outlined in their submitted CVs, and the motivations expressed in their registration forms.

On Day 1 participants engaged in a series of activities, adopting an approach oriented towards participatory learning. The session started with a welcome and introduction that explained the goals and format of the two-day learning event. Keywords essential for assessing socio-economic policies were provided by the lecturer. Subsequently, group discussions took place where participants collaborated to generate ideas, define concepts, and discuss challenges associated with the specific keywords assigned to them. The program then included group presentations to delve into the meaning and exploration of the keywords.

Following a break, the lecturer provided theoretical insights into policy design and evaluation, incorporating ideas and discussions from the earlier group work. The day concluded with a Question and Answer session.

On Day 2 the focus shifted to the role of the FOSSR project in providing essential methodological and data resources for policy design and evaluation. Participants were then tasked with a policy evaluation exercise in groups, followed by group presentations. The day

² Learning Session, 6-7 December 2023: <https://zenodo.org/records/10390304>
Action research session, 13 and 20 March 2024: <https://zenodo.org/records/10571855>

concluded with a segment highlighting the important role of FOSSR in the potential for policy learning.

The main objective of this Learning Session was to provide a comprehensive understanding of the process of designing and evaluating socio-economic policies. This was achieved by incorporating insights from both theoretical viewpoints and group exercises, all within a participatory learning approach.

A detailed report of the Session, with more data on contents, participants and assessment results is provided in *Annex 6*.

4.3 Description of the first Action Research Session

The first FOSSR Action research session “*Transformative paths in research practices: co-developing social science infrastructures*”, which took place in two meetings on 13 and 20 March 2024, one week apart, had two specific objectives:

- to propose some fundamentals of the methodology to produce social transformation and develop critical reflection in the actors involved;
- to enhance the transformative potential offered by research infrastructures, through data, tools, and methods developed within FOSSR.

The two objectives were linked by an innovative action research approach elaborated at CNR-IRCrES by Erica Rizziato (curator of the session) aimed at co-generating useful information both for:

- participants, about the real need for information they could request from FOSSR to improve the impact of their work
- the FOSSR team, who would facilitate interactive modalities useful to shape the services and tools developed by the project in order to make it easily and usefully usable by the beneficiaries.

The First Action research Session was open to everyone, with no specific requirements regarding prior knowledge or competencies. However, due to the highly participative nature of the methodology, the number of participants was limited to 21. Selection has been based on the motivational statements included in the registration forms.

While the sessions has been also attended remotely via a digital connection, physical attendance was recommended in the Call for participation to fully exploit the learning experience. The action research session was structured over two days, spaced one week apart, to allow time for critical reflections between meetings. Therefore, attending both days was strongly recommended to fully benefit from the experience.

The session was conducted in Italian, but all materials, including thematic literature and notes on the topics covered, was available in English for all participants.

The Session was organized by CNR-IRCrES as part of the FOSSR project, with the local scientific and organizing committee comprising Erica Rizziato, Serena Fabrizio, Andrea Orazio Spinello, Rita Giuffredi, Alessandra Maria Stilo, and Emanuela Reale.

This comprehensive and engaging format ensures a robust participative learning experience, fostering critical reflections and collaborative knowledge generation among participants.

The first day of the session started with a welcome and opening remarks by Andrea Orazio Spinello, coordinator of WP8 from CNR-IRCrES. Serena Fabrizio, responsible of the 8.2 task from CNR-IRCrES elaborated on the significance of the action research sessions in FOSSR. Erica Rizzati from CNR-IRCrES then delved into the fundamentals of action research and the specific methodology applied in this session.

The morning session concluded with an interactive exercise aimed at generating a development question. After a lunch break, participants engaged in another interactive exercise focusing on learning by doing in interaction.

The day wrapped up with a follow-up discussion on development questions and next steps in interaction with the FOSSR team.

The second day started with feedback from participants regarding the development question. An interactive exercise followed, exploring a process of change with dynamic design.

After a lunch break, participants engaged once again in learning by doing in interaction. The session concluded with a follow-up discussion in interaction with the FOSSR team, discussing next steps also related to the potential of FOSSR activities.

A detailed report of the Session, with more data on contents, participants and assessment results is provided in *Annex 7*.

4.4 Feedback and evaluation of the participatory sessions

Both sessions met with considerable interest both in terms of social following of the launch and follow-up posts for both events and interest in the topics and materials produced. The table below summarizes the number of views of the posts launched to promote them³ and downloads and views of the materials for both in Zenodo.

Table 3 – Views and download of materials from the participatory sessions from Zenodo.

<i>Participatory Session</i>	<i>Materials on Zenodo⁴</i>
Learning Session "Designing Socio-Economic Policy Evaluation: learning through FOSSR"	Views 67 Downloads 101
Action Research Session "Transformative paths in research practices: co-developing social science infrastructures"	Views 52 Downloads 67

For both sessions participants produced an assessment through filling a questionnaire. Participants of the FOSSR Learning Session highlighted several key aspects of their experience. They appreciated the "learning by doing" approach, which emphasized

³ For details see *Deliverable 9.4 First report on communication, dissemination and outreach*.

⁴ Data updated to: April 2024

collaboration and interaction among participants. The sessions fostered involvement and active learning through discussion and teamwork within the classroom, creating a dynamic and engaging environment. The interactive lessons and team-based activities were particularly praised, as they allowed for stimulating and meaningful exchanges.

Participants noted that the teaching methodology was innovative, and the discussions were both interesting and enriching. A standout feature of the course was the opportunity to interact with peers who were either passionate about or experts in the topic. The course was well-structured, effectively covering policy design and its implementation. The chance to present their designs and discuss them with the trainer and fellow students was found to be highly valuable. Overall, the laboratory activities and group discussions were seen as particularly stimulating and beneficial for deepening understanding and fostering collaborative learning.

Figure 1. Overall satisfaction of the Learning Session

Note. The figure reports only the responses received (13 out of 23 participants).

Participants of the Action Research Session particularly appreciated the blend of theoretical components with subsequent discussions and the application of principles, noting that this structure ensures a comprehensive understanding and practical application of the concepts learned.

The interactive roll-out of the FOSSR sessions emphasizes practical learning through exercises, making the learning process itself an action-oriented experience (Action Learning within Action Research). This approach aligns with the FOSSR beneficiaries' vision, focusing on interaction and practical exercises. The best insights come from extracting driving principles from observed individual and organizational behaviors.

Figure 2. Overall satisfaction of the Action Research Session

Note. The figure reports only the responses received (9 out of 21 participants).

A detailed report of assessment results for both sessions is provided in *Annexes 6 and 7*.

5. REPORT ON COURSE AT MASTER LEVEL

FOSSR funds a course at Master level (Master Universitario) on data science applied to the social sciences – Master in Social Data Science (SDS) –, established at University of Milan Bicocca. As per the objectives of the Project, this Master programme is intended to promote a widespread knowledge of methodologies used in the empirical social sciences and the training of a new generation of young researchers with strong expertise in the application to social science of techniques of data collection, processing, analysis, visualization, reporting in a variety of situation. The Master Programme allows students to acquire a title pertaining to the third cycle of the Bologna process (Level 8 EQF).

5.1 Steps for establishing the Master Programme

As reported in the D8.1, for the activation of the Master it was necessary to identify a suitable university. The University of Milan Bicocca was found to be a particularly suitable one. In fact, together with the CNR, the university is the national node of the European research infrastructure CESSDA, one of the three research infrastructures composing the network to be reinforced through the FOSSR project. Also, among the missions of CESSDA there is the facilitation in teaching and learning in the social sciences. Putting together the objectives of CESSDA and the FOSSR project, the University, with its many years of experience in the field of specific research and training activities, appeared therefore the ideal candidate for the establishment of the Master. Following an invitation from the leader unit of WP8 (CNR-IRCrES protocol no. 0000786_2022 of 22 November 2022), an expression of interest to organize the Master Programme was received from University of Milan Bicocca, Department of Sociology and Social Research (CNR-IRCrES protocol no. 0000789_2022 of 23 November 2022). The aforementioned department presented a detailed proposal for structuring a Second-level Master Programme (*Master di Secondo Livello*), suggesting a new name – Master in “Social Data Science” – instead of “Master of Applied Data Science”, as foreseen in the Project DoW. Therefore, it was decided to sign

an agreement between the CNR and the university within the framework of the existing Framework Agreement between the University of Milan Bicocca and the National Research Council dated May 14, 2019.

In the following months, CNR-IRCrES initiated discussions with the University of Milan Bicocca to refine the objectives of the Master programme and the Study Plan, which should have demonstrated high quality and content suitable for transferring knowledge of advanced techniques applied to social sciences, enabling the utilization of large datasets and conducting computational social research. The Master programme in SDS was finally conceived as a **two-year programme that integrates social sciences and computer science**, focusing on the analysis of Big Data and the utilization of Artificial Intelligence algorithms alongside social scientific theory. SDS wants to offer a strong foundation in Data Science for students with a social science background, with a primary emphasis on computational science applied to social science research. The programme aims to equip students with valuable skills sought after in the job market and allows them to apply computational and statistical techniques to address important societal issues. The Master programme involves the acquisition of **120 CFUs** for the two years and consists of around 750 hour of classes in **remote mode** and laboratory and stage activities.

On August 2023, the signing of the **Agreement between CNR-IRCrES and the University of Milan-Bicocca** (Protocol CNR no. 247818 dated 10-08-2023) for the establishment of the Second Level Master programme in Social Data Science has been completed, marking the achievement of milestone 4 of WP8: *Agreement with university for the course at Master level*.

5.2 Launch of the call and selection of the students

The **public call for applications** to the Master Programme was launched on September 27, 2023 (*Annex 8*). The call included the composition of the **Master SDS scientific committee**, chaired by Prof. Sonia Stefanizzi from the Department of Sociology and Social Research of University of Milan-Bicocca. Other members include Prof. Francesco Mazzeo Rinaldi from the University of Catania, Dr. Andrea Orazio Spinello from CNR-IRCrES, Prof. Giovanni Giuffrida from the University of Catania, Prof. Davide Bennato from the University of Catania, and Prof. Mark Coté from King's College London. Prof. Sonia Stefanizzi serves as the director of the Master Programme, while Mariangela Tommasone, from the Department of Sociology and Social Research, serves as the program's organizational secretary. The Master also opened a website at <https://sds.sociologia.unimib.it/>

The call foresaw **26 positions for the students**. There are **no costs for students** attending the Master programme, as it is fully funded by the FOSSR Project. Candidates applying for the Master programme must hold one of the following qualifications: - Master's Degree in one of the following classes: LM-88 Sociology and Social Research; LM-82 Statistics; LM-18 Computer Science; LM-56 Economics; - Specialized Degrees or those obtained under the Previous Regulations (prior to DM 509/99), considered equivalent; - Equivalent foreign

qualifications. Preferred qualifications include candidates' motivation and their familiarity with the fundamental themes of methodology and statistics in social research.

The **selection process** took place through online interviews on 23 October 2023. A total of 42 candidates applied, out of which 39 were admitted (3 candidates were not admitted to the interview due to lack of qualifications). Three candidates were absent during the interview, and three withdrew, resulting in a total of 33 candidates examined. The publication of the ranking list occurred on 26 October 2024, with 26 candidates admitted to the Master programme (including one student for the extracurricular position reserved for the university's technical-administrative staff) and 7 deemed eligible but not admitted (*Annex 9*). During the initial months, two students withdrew due to balancing commitments between the Master programme and work obligations. Consequently, two additional students were admitted from the waiting list. Furthermore, four students exceeded the maximum allowable absences and are therefore disqualified from obtaining the degree. **At April 2024, 22 students are regularly attending.**

5.3 Plan of Study of the Master Programme in SDS

In the Plan of Study the Master scheduled **12 subjects/modules for the first year.**

The Master Programme started on **November 9, 2023**. Table 4 displays the subjects scheduled for the first year of the Master programme, along with the corresponding assigned teachers for each subject.

Table 4 – Subjects/modules foreseen in the first year of Plan of Study of the Master SDS.

<i>Subject</i>	<i>Teacher</i>	<i>From-To</i>
Fundamental of social science research design	Tatiana Lysova	Nov 9, 2024- Jan 25, 2024
Element of statistics, probabilistic reasoning, and R	Jonah Lynch	Nov 9, 2024- Jan 26, 2024
Computer programming (Python)	Alessandro Ortis	Nov 10, 2024- Jan 26, 2024
Digital Sociology	Davide Bennato	Feb 1, 2024- Mar 11, 2024
Notions of Database Management Systems	Salvatore Nicotra	Feb 1, 2024- Mar 7, 2024
Basic Social Network Analysis	Vincenzo Franco Bonnici	Feb 9, 2024- Mar 8, 2024
Linguistic theories and computational linguistics	Marco Venuti	Mar 14, 2024- Apr 19, 2024

Logic and causal reasoning	Tatiana Lysova	Mar 28, 2024- Apr 19, 2024
Non-relational Database Management Systems	Vincenzo Franco Bonnici	Mar 14, 2024- Apr 18, 2024
Artificial Intelligence Introduction	Giovanni Giuffrida	May 2, 2024- Jun 14, 2024
AI Algorithms (Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing...)	Rosalba Giugno	May 2, 2024- Jun 7, 2024
AI Algorithms for Social Science	Francesco Amato	May 3, 2024- Jun 20, 2024

With only minor adjustments, such as the occasional shifting of two or three classes between instructors or rescheduling agreed upon with students, the calendar has been adhered to as initially planned at the beginning of the program. **Classes are conducted online via the Moodle platform every Thursday and Friday from 9:00 AM to 1:00 PM and from 2:00 PM to 6:00 PM.**

Additionally, the Master SDS Scientific Committee has endorsed a two or three hours **seminar schedule** led by representatives of the FOSSR project, aimed at introducing specific topics developed within the project (Table 5).

Table 5 – Seminars foreseen in the first year of the Master SDS (Summer 2024).

<i>Title of the seminar</i>	<i>Teacher</i>	<i>From-To</i>
The Ontology and Practice of Machine Learning	Giovanni Cerulli	Jun 21, 2024
Causal Bayesian Networks	Lorenzo Giammei	Jun 21, 2024
Value and potential of Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences	Andrea Orazio Spinello, Emanuela Varinetti	Jun 27, 2024
The whys and hows of science communication. Communication of science and stakeholders engagement in Social Science Research Infrastructures	Serena Fabrizio, Rita Giuffredi, Elisa Storace	Jul 4, 2024
Exponential Random Graph Models: estimation and applications	Antonio Zinilli	Jul 5, 2024

6. REPORT ON PHD POSITIONS

6.1 Design and organization of FOSSR PhD positions

According to the project DoW approved, **the FOSSR project funded PhD positions in doctoral courses at various Italian universities during the thirty-ninth Italian doctoral cycle (XXIX ciclo di dottorato)**. The positions were assigned in response to research project proposals coherent to the themes of the FOSSR project or the advancement of infrastructures networked in the project, with the goal of developing advanced skills in the field of social sciences, fostering effective research methodologies, allowing advanced analysis of complex data sets, and preparing to a complex use of statistical software.

PhD positions are valuable in feeding a new generation of scholars who can use the resources provided by the RIs involved in FOSSR by combining strong theoretical, methodological, and technical knowledge, as well as being aware of the legal issues related to data processing.

For PhD positions, candidates were required to submit research projects and/or social sciences or methodological issues on topics developed by the FOSSR project, such as Innovation in data collection (WP3), Longitudinal studies (WP4), Innovation in data analysis: knowledge extraction, integration, and enrichment (WP5), Data access services related to research infrastructure (WP6).

The PhD positions were realized through **specific agreements with universities with which the CNR has already signed the General Agreement for Research Cooperation**. The signed agreements fell within the framework of the XXIX (39th) cycle of the Italian PhD program, starting from the 2023/2024 academic year.

Considering the beginning of the PhD programs in the period between August and November 2023 and the FOSSR project's deadline of April 30, 2025, the need to plan the PhD scholarships arose immediately taking into account that FOSSR could only cover the funding of the **first two years of scholarship**. The CNR promptly addressed this issue by providing for the coverage of the subsequent years of scholarship either with its own funds or those of the university with which the agreement would be activated. This process also resulted in a **reduction in the number of doctoral positions to be activated** compared to what was planned in the project's DoW, from 20 to 11. This change was agreed with the MUR.

In compliance with the project guidelines, which required the creation of PhD scholarships to be equally distributed between universities in the South and in Central-Northern Italy, three CNR institutes — IRCrES (with units in Turin and Rome), ISTC (with units in Rome and Catania), and IRPPS (with units in Rome and Fisciano) — identified universities compatible in profile and experience with the strategic objectives of FOSSR.

Letters of intent were sent to these universities, followed by meetings to specifically define 11 PhD positions and to outline the financial coverage after the two years of FOSSR funding.

The first list of universities and PhD positions is as follows:

1. University of Trento (1 position in the PhD program in Sustainability: Economics, Environment, Management, and Society, activated by CNR-IRCrES);
2. University of Rome La Sapienza (2 positions in the PhD School of Social and Economic Sciences, activated by CNR-IRCrES);
3. University of Milan Bocconi (1 position in the PhD program in Social and Political Science, activated by CNR-IRPPS);
4. University of Milan Statale (2 positions in the PhD program in Economic Sociology, Organizational Management, and Labor Studies: 1 activated by CNR-IRPPS, 1 activated by CNR-ISTC);
5. University of Bologna Alma Mater (1 position in the PhD program in Philosophy, Science, Cognition, and Semiotics, activated by CNR-ISTC);
6. University of Naples Federico II (SOUTH, 2 positions in the PhD program in Social and Statistical Sciences, activated by CNR-IRPPS);
7. University of Catania (SOUTH, 2 positions: 1 in the PhD program in Political Sciences, activated by CNR-IRCRES, and 1 in the PhD program in Computer Science, activated by CNR-ISTC).

At the end of the process, due to bureaucratic and organizational reasons, the second scholarship planned with the University of Milan Statale and CNR-ISTC was not finalized, resulting in a total of **10 PhD scholarships being defined**, with 6 at Central-Northern universities and 4 at Southern universities. The signing of the agreements for the activation 10 PhD positions marked the achievement of milestone 5 of WP8: *Agreements with universities for PhD positions*.

The detailed list of activated PhD positions is provided in the Table 6, which comprehensively represents crucial information. These details include:

- **Protocol:** provides a unique identifier for each agreement, simplifying the reference and management of each activated PhD position.
- **CNR Institute:** indicates the CNR Institute that signed the agreement for the activation of the PhD program.
- **University:** indicates the University that signed the agreement for the activation of the PhD program.
- **CNR Contact:** identifies the CNR scientific coordinators associated with the individual PhD program, offering support and/or assistance during the PhD course.
- **University Contact:** identifies the University's scientific coordinators associated with the individual PhD program, offering support and/or assistance during the PhD study program.
- **Area:** specifies the geographical location of the PhD program. Of the 10 activated PhD programs, 6 are in the North and 4 are in the South.

- **Funding Sources:** describes the anticipated funding sources for the financial coverage of the 10 activated PhD positions to ensure the continuity of financial support. The first two years are covered with FOSSR funds, while for the subsequent years, other funding sources are used (e.g., FOE CESSDA, FOE RISIS, etc.).
- **PhD:** represents the scientific sector in which the PhD program will focus; the study theme and title will be determined later and, in some cases, approved upon entering the second academic year, as provided by the university PhD regulations.
- **Winner:** identifies the winning candidate for each activated PhD program.
- **Start Date:** indicates the start date of the PhD program for the selected candidate.

In accordance with Ministerial Decree no. 1141 of 7 October 2021 by MUR, within projects financed under the funding scheme “Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca” the Consortium must ensure compliance with constraints arising from the NRRP about gender inequality, thus at least 40% of PhD grants must be awarded to female researchers. With relation to this decree 50% of FOSSR PhD has been awarded to female researchers.

Table 6 – List of PhD positions activated by the FOSSR Project.

N	PROTOCOL	CNR INSTITUTE	CNR CONTACT	UNIVERSITY	UNIVERSITY CONTACT	AREA	FUNDING SOURCES	YEARS	PhD	WINNER	START DATE
1	183971/2023	IRCrES	A.Zinilli	Trento	R.Raffelli	NORTH	FOSSR RISIS	3	Sustainability: Economics, Environment, Management and Society (SUSTEEMS)	De Palma Alessandro	Nov 1, 2023
2	153738/2023	IRCrES	A.Zinilli	RM Sapienza	R.Cerqueti	NORTH	FOSSR RISIS	3	Science of Science: Analysys of complex systems in Science, Technology and Innovation (STI)	Micarelli Andrea	Nov 1, 2023
3	153738/2023	IRCrES	E.Reale	RM Sapienza	R.Cerqueti E.Reale	NORTH	FOSSR RISIS	3	Government R&D funding policies: design and implementation	Carino Flavia D.	Nov 1, 2023
4	121618/2023	IRPPS	A.Paparusso F.Heins	MI Bocconi	L.Mencarini	NORTH	FOSSR CESSDA	4	Social and Political Science	Perotti Matilde	Sept 1, 2023
5	248151/2023	IRPPS	M.Paolucci	MI Statale	F.Squazzoni	NORTH	FOSSR CESSDA	4	Economy Sociology, Organization and Labor (ESOL)	Sandretto Riccardo	Oct 1, 2023

6	414577/2023	ISTC	A.Nuzzolese	Bologna	C.Paolucci A.Gangemi	NORTH	FOSSR UNIV	3	Philosophy, Science, Cognition and Semiotics	Chinchella Nicola	Nov 2023	1,
7	166892/2023	IRCrES	A.O.Spinello	Catania	C.Pennisi	SOUTH	FOSSR RISIS	3	Political Science	Occhipinti Ornella	Aug 2023	1,
8	188907/2023	IRPPS	P.Landri S.Stefanizzi	NA Federico II	E.Amaturo	SOUTH	FOSSR CESSDA	3	Social Sciences and Statistics	Sacco Dario	Nov 2023	6,
9	188907/2023	IRPPS	P.Landri S.Stefanizzi	NA Federico II	E.Amaturo	SOUTH	FOSSR CESSDA	3	Social Sciences and Statistics	Ambrosio Caterina	Nov 2023	6,
10	204259/2023	ISTC	M.Mongiovì A.Nuzzolese	Catania	S.Battiato	SOUTH	FOSSR UNIV	2	Computer Science	Tuccari S. Giusy Giulia	Aug 2023	1,

6.2 Management and reporting of FOSSR PhD positions

The management of FOSSR PhD positions involved a range of complex activities, including the selection and admission of candidates, academic supervision, and the monitoring of students' progress. Each stage of the PhD path requires careful planning and efficient coordination to ensure that students can develop the skills and knowledge necessary to conduct high-quality research.

Reporting, on the other hand, involves detailed documentation of the progress and activities of PhD students, as well as the management of allocated funds and resources. It is crucial for academic institutions to maintain accurate records that reflect the research activities, publications, conference participations, and other academic achievements of PhD students. This not only facilitates the evaluation of PhD programs but is also essential for transparency towards funders and regulatory authorities.

In summary, effective management and reporting of PhD positions not only support students in their academic journey but also contribute to the reputation and sustainability of academic institutions. Through well-structured management practices and transparent reporting, it is possible to create an academic environment that promotes excellence in research and the continuous development of knowledge.

In order to manage and report the FOSSR PhD position even in compliance with the “Linee guida per la rendicontazione degli investimenti destinati alle infrastrutture di ricerca M4C2” the **CNR-ISMED team designed a process** with some templates summarized in the document named “Guida Elenco documentazione dottorati” (*Annex 10*).

Furthermore a Teams channel FOSSR PHD-grp was created as repository of all documents and as communication tool with students and university Staff.

The **scientific reporting process** for doctoral courses includes a set of detailed structured templates designed to monitor the progress of students and research projects during the doctoral course. The templates used are:

- **Letter of Acceptance:** this document, signed at the beginning of the doctoral course, confirms the student's admission to the program of study. It contains information on the student's biographical data (name and surname, place and date of birth, social security number, residence, etc.) and important information on the responsibilities to carry out the research activities envisaged in the program, with the understanding that failure to comply with all the vertical, horizontal and cross-cutting principles will result in withdrawal of the grant (*Annex 11*).

- **Bimonthly Reports:** Bimonthly reports are regular reports that students must complete in detail to report progress during each two-month period. These reports include descriptions of study activities during that period, attendance at educational and/or training events (e.g., conferences, symposia, seminars, etc.), preparation of bibliographies, scientific reports, and research articles preparatory to the completion of the doctoral program (*Annex 12*).

- **Annual Scientific Report:** In addition to being the comprehensive document summarizing the work accomplished during the academic year, the annual report is used as a tool to assess consistency with the goals set in the research project. In addition to providing a detailed overview of the activities carried out and the results obtained, this report also highlights the development of the student's critical thinking, new findings in the research area, and the

practical and theoretical implications of the results obtained. In addition, the annual report can provide an opportunity to reflect on the methodologies used, research strategies adopted, and future prospects for the progress and development of the doctoral project (*Annex 13*).

These documents are essential tools for the continuous and in-depth evaluation of doctoral students' academic progress. In addition to tracking students' progress, these documents make it possible to identify any deviations from study and research plans at an early stage, providing a detailed picture of the activities carried out and the results achieved over time. In addition, through periodic review of the reports, work and research strategies can be adjusted as necessary, identifying strengths and areas that require further investigation. This monitoring and evaluation process helps not only to ensure compliance with set goals, but also to foster the professional and academic development of doctoral students in successfully pursuing the completion of their education.

7. THE VALUE OF COMMUNICATION FOR PROMOTING TRAINING ACTIVITIES: THE CONNECTION BETWEEN WP8 AND WP9

Effective communication activities are essential for promoting training opportunities, leveraging both social media and internal communication channels to effectively reach the targets of online courses and participatory sessions, as well as to disseminate information about the Master programme and the creation of the PhD positions. Exploiting the potential of social media platforms allows for prompt dissemination of information, timely updates, engagement with potential participants, and reaching a global audience. Concurrently, robust internal communication ensures that all stakeholders, including staff, are well-informed and can advocate for these opportunities. Together, these efforts enhance visibility, encourage participation, and foster a community of learning and growth.

In this respect, **WP9 of the FOSSR project**, coordinated by CNR-IRCrES, played a fundamental role in ensuring effective communication by accompanying each training opportunity with a proper communication campaign in collaboration with the task leaders and the organizers of the trainings. By leveraging various media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.) and strategic messaging, WP9 heightened awareness and engagement for the training opportunities. These campaigns provided clear and compelling information, highlighting the benefits and relevance of each training session.

As a result, WP9 not only increased participation to WP8 initiatives but also built a stronger, more informed community of researchers and stakeholders. This approach to communication ensured that the training opportunities reached a wide audience, maximizing their potential impact.

Efforts made by WP9 team are described in the related WP9 deliverables of the FOSSR project.

8. NEXT MILESTONES AND KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Table 7 presents the list of **remaining milestones** foreseen in the FOSSR DoW, in relation to the task 8.1 and 8.2, the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) expected and the deadline. No milestones are foreseen in relation to Task 8.3.

Due to the six-month extension obtained by the FOSSR project to October 31, 2025, the responsible of Task 8.1 and 8.2 have decided to postpone the deadline for achieving the remaining milestones (11 and 12) by 1 bimester compared to what was indicated in the DoW (from bimester 15 to bimester 16). Below are the new deadlines.

Table 7 – Remaining Milestones and KPIs related to Task 8.1 and Task 8.2

Milestone number	Milestone	WP Task	KPI	Deadline
11	Second 3 Online courses delivered (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	3 courses delivered 75 attendees involved	Bimester 16 June 2025
12	Second 2 Learning session/Action Research sessions delivered	Task 8.2	2 Learning session/ Action Research Sessions delivered; 40 participants involved	Bimester 16 June 2025

8.1 Next WP8 deliverable expected for the WP8 Task 8.1, 8.2 and 8.3

Due to the six-month extension obtained by the FOSSR project to October 31, 2025, and the postposition of the remaining milestones connected to Tasks 8.1 and 8.2, the preparation of the associated deliverable (D8.5) was also postponed by two months compared to what was indicated in the DoW (from M30 to M32). Below is the new deadline.

- **D8.5** Second Report on initiatives related to capacity building and training (online courses, learning session and action research session, higher education courses).
- Due to **M32 (June 2025)**.

9. CONCLUSIONS

This Deliverable have demonstrated the **achievement of milestones 8 and 10 associated with WP8 of the FOSSR Project**. This paper summarizes the features of the initiatives and reports their development. Through the organization of online courses, participatory sessions, and activation of higher education programmes, FOSSR aims to enhance the skills the capabilities of current and next generation of researchers, data scientists and relevant stakeholders in accessing, managing, and analyzing social science data.

Three online training courses, two participatory sessions (one Learning Session and one Action Research Session) were organized, a Master Programme in Social Data Science was activated, and ten doctoral fellowships were funded. Three more online courses and 2 more participatory sessions (one Learning Session and one Action Research Session) will be promoted in the second part of the Project, and the progress of the Master and doctoral tracks will be monitored.

10.LIST OF ANNEXES

- Annex 1** – OTC Reports
- Annex 2** – OTC Standard Operating Procedure
- Annex 3** – OTC Call for courses
- Annex 4** – OTC Template for proposals
- Annex 5** – Template for expression of interest in FOSSR participatory sessions (survey on training needs)
- Annex 6** – Report on the first FOSSR Learning Session
- Annex 7** – Report on the first FOSSR Action Research Session
- Annex 8** – Public call for applications for the Master Programme in SDS
- Annex 9** – Publication of the ranking list for accessing the Master Programme in SDS
- Annex 10** – Documentation List Guide for PhD positions
- Annex 11** – Template of the Letter of acceptance for FOSSR PhD positions
- Annex 12** – Template of bimonthly report for FOSSR PhD positions
- Annex 13** – Template of annual scientific report for the FOSSR PhD positions

11.LIST OF ACRONYMS

Table 8 – List of acronyms and meaning

ACRONYM	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARS	Action Research Session
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CFU	Credito Formativo Universitario (University Educational Credit)
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-IRCrES	Istituto di Ricerca sulla Crescita Economica Sostenibile del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Research Institute on Sustainable Economic Growth of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-IRPPS	Istituto delle Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-ISMED	Istituto di Studi sul Mediterraneo del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Studies on the Mediterranean of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-ISTC	Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie della Cognizione del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Cognitive Sciences and Technologies of the National Research Council of Italy)
DoW	Description of Work
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
ESOL	Economy Sociology, Organization and Labor
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FOE	Fondo Ordinario per gli Enti e le istituzioni di ricerca (Ordinary fund for research organizations and institutions)
FOSSR	Fostering Open science in Social Science Research
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information and Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LM	Laurea Magistrale (Master's degree)

LS	Learning Session
M(X)	Month (number)
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (Italian Minister of University and Research)
MC	Methodological Course
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NRRP	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
OTC	Online Training Course
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PhD	Philosophiae Doctor
PRP	Main Promoters
PS	Participatory Session
R&D	Research and Development
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDMC	Research Data Management Course
RI	Research Infrastructure
RISIS	Research Infrastructure for Science, technology and Innovation policy Studies
RML	RDF Mapping Language
SDS	Social Data Science
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
STI	Science Technology and Innovation
SUSTEEMS	Sustainability: Economics, Environment, Management and Society
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
UO	Unità Operativa (Operating Unit)
WP	Work Package